

ACO-RNN: A MULTI-OBJECTIVE ANT COLONY OPTIMIZATION AND RECURRENT NEURAL NETWORK FRAMEWORK FOR DISASTER TWEET SUMMARIZATION

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ABSTRACT

The rapid growth of disaster-related content on social media offers valuable opportunities for situational awareness, yet it also creates major challenges due to noise, redundancy, and the rapidly evolving nature of crisis events. Existing disaster tweet summarization approaches, including ontology-based, embedding-based, and neural methods, typically address semantic relevance, redundancy reduction, or coherence in isolation. As a result, they struggle to simultaneously control redundancy, preserve temporal coherence, and remain scalable for real-time disaster response. This study is motivated by the need for a unified summarization framework that jointly addresses these challenges within a single, scalable, and unsupervised model. To this end, we propose Ant Colony Optimization and Recurrent Neural Network (ACO-RNN), a hybrid framework that integrates Word2Vec embeddings for semantic representation, Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) for redundancy-aware sentence selection, and a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) to preserve sequential coherence across selected tweets. The summarization task is formulated as a multi-objective optimization problem that balances relevance, coverage, and diversity while minimizing redundancy. The proposed framework is evaluated on four benchmark disaster tweet datasets, namely TyHagupit, SandyHShoot, HydBlast, and UFlood, using Recall-Oriented Understudy for Gisting Evaluation (ROUGE) metrics. Experimental results show that ACO-RNN achieves ROUGE-1 F1-scores ranging from 0.587 to 0.614, with relative improvements of 8 to 13 percent over strong baseline methods, including OntoDSumm and IKDSumm, along with consistent gains in ROUGE-2 and ROUGE-L. These findings demonstrate that combining redundancy-aware optimization with sequential neural modeling effectively overcomes key limitations of existing approaches and produces concise, coherent, and informative summaries suitable for disaster response and situational awareness.

Keywords: *Disaster Tweets; Word2Vec; Text Summarization; Ant Colony Optimization; Recurrent Neural Networks.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Social media platforms, particularly X (formerly Twitter), have become crucial sources of real-time information during disasters and crises [1]. In such events, millions of tweets are posted, offering critical updates, assistance information, and situational awareness. With the increasing frequency and severity of natural and man-made disasters, such as hurricanes, earthquakes, wildfires, and industrial accidents [2], there is a pressing need for efficient methods to process and summarize the overwhelming volume of online data. This surge of information holds significant potential to improve the understanding of disaster progression, assess impacts, and identify immediate on-the-ground

needs [3]. This stream of user-generated content offers valuable situational awareness but is massive, noisy, and rapidly evolving, making manual monitoring impractical. The unfiltered and redundant nature of posts often obscures critical signals and slows down decision-making, highlighting the need for automated solutions [4].

Summarization plays a crucial role in disaster management, as large amounts of information are disseminated from various sources, including social media, television, newspapers, and magazines [5]. Compiling information from such diverse channels and making the best decisions to handle the disaster can be an overwhelming task. Without a thorough understanding of the impacts and characteristics of

different types of disasters, disaster management efforts can be ineffective [6]. Effective risk management, coordination, communication, and planning are key elements that administrators must address to successfully manage disasters [7]. Accurate and timely information is crucial, as administrations have limited time to respond to disasters. The goal of automatic summarization is to extract critical, consistent information without the need to process every detail [8].

The challenge is intensified by three key factors: volume, noise, and redundancy. Tweets are short, informal, and often filled with hashtags, slang, or abbreviations [9], which complicates natural language processing. Many users repost similar updates, creating redundancy that can drown out novel information [10]. In fast-moving disasters, thousands of posts can appear within minutes, as seen in the 2023 Morocco earthquake and the 2024 floods in southern Brazil, overwhelming response teams with repeated or irrelevant content [11] [12]. Scalable, real-time summarization methods are therefore essential to extract key updates and support time-sensitive decision-making.

Automatic text summarization has emerged as a promising solution for condensing large collections of short messages into concise and informative digests [7]. Several approaches have been proposed, including ontology-based methods such as OntoDSumm [13] and OntoRealSumm [14], keyphrase-guided extractive techniques like IKDSumm [15], and abstractive neural models such as ATSumm [16]. While these methods have advanced the state of the art, they continue to face notable limitations. Ontology-driven approaches rely heavily on predefined concept hierarchies, which limit their ability to adapt to emerging terminology and informal language during novel disasters. Neural and embedding-based approaches enhance semantic representation but often lack explicit redundancy control or incur high computational costs, reducing their suitability for real-time, high-velocity. Recent studies demonstrate how these technologies have been applied in practical disaster tweet summarization scenarios. OntoDSumm has been employed to align tweets with disaster-specific concepts to improve relevance and reduce noise, while OntoRealSumm extends this idea to streaming environments by generating incremental summaries for evolving disaster events [13] [14]. Embedding-based extractive systems such as IKDSumm integrate key phrases with contextual representations to improve the selection of informative and situation-aware tweets [15].

Abstractive approaches like ATSumm leverage auxiliary information to generate fluent summaries under sparse training data conditions, highlighting the potential of neural generation models in disaster contexts [16]. In addition, the introduction of annotated resources such as ADSumm has supported supervised and hybrid summarization systems by providing ground-truth summaries for evaluation across multiple disaster events [17]. Optimization-based techniques, including multi-objective ant colony optimization methods, have also been applied to microblog summarization tasks to balance coverage, diversity, and redundancy [19] [20]. In practical disaster response settings, these systems are commonly used to support situational awareness by filtering large volumes of social media content, identifying actionable information such as damage reports or resource needs, and generating concise summaries that assist emergency managers in rapid decision-making.

Despite these advances, no existing approach sufficiently addresses redundancy reduction, semantic coverage, and temporal coherence within a single unified framework. This study is motivated by the observation that effective disaster tweet summarization requires jointly controlling redundancy and relevance while preserving the sequential flow of information that reflects event progression. Optimization-based methods are well suited for balancing coverage and diversity, whereas neural sequence models are effective in maintaining contextual and temporal coherence. Integrating these complementary strengths provides a principled way to overcome the fragmented treatment of these challenges in prior work and to generate summaries that are both informative and coherent under real-world disaster conditions.

To address these challenges, this paper proposes Ant Colony Optimization and Recurrent Neural Network (ACO-RNN), a hybrid summarization framework that integrates Word2Vec embeddings for semantic representation, Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) for redundancy-aware tweet selection, and a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) for preserving temporal coherence across selected tweets. The framework formulates summarization as a multi-objective optimization task that explicitly balances coverage, diversity, and relevance while minimizing redundancy. By combining metaheuristic optimization with neural sequence modeling, the proposed approach produces summaries that are semantically rich, concise, and logically structured, enabling decision-makers to

quickly grasp key developments during evolving disaster situations.

The key contributions of this work can be summarized as follows:

- We introduce a hybrid framework that unifies optimization-based selection with neural modeling to address redundancy and coherence simultaneously.
- We formulate the summarization problem as a multi-objective optimization task, enabling a principled trade-off between coverage, diversity, and redundancy.
- We conduct extensive experiments on four benchmark disaster tweet datasets (TyHagupit, SandyHShoot, HydBlast, and UFlood), demonstrating consistent improvements over ontology-based, clustering-based, and neural baselines in terms of ROUGE-1, ROUGE-2, and ROUGE-L.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews related work on disaster tweet summarization, Section 3 describes the proposed ACO-RNN framework, including preprocessing, semantic representation, and optimization-based selection, Section 4 presents the results, and Section 5 concludes with insights into the framework's scalability and future research directions.

2. RELATED WORKS

The surge of research on disaster-related social media summarization reflects the pressing need to turn massive, fast-moving streams of posts into concise, actionable insights for crisis response. Social media platforms provide first-hand reports, but the content is short, noisy, and highly redundant, which complicates automated analysis. Researchers have therefore explored a range of strategies ontology-based classification, embedding-driven extraction, optimization-based selection, and hybrid neural approaches to address these challenges, each with its own strengths and shortcomings.

Ontology-based methods were among the earliest attempts to bring structure to disaster communication. OntoDSumm [13] aligned tweets with a predefined disaster ontology, improving conceptual coverage and filtering noise, while OntoRealSumm [14] extended this approach to streaming scenarios, producing summaries that update in near real time. These methods improved

interpretability but are limited by their dependence on fixed ontologies, which struggle to capture new terminology and slang emerging during novel crises.

To capture richer semantics, researchers have moved toward embedding-based and key-phrase-guided approaches. IKDSumm [15] integrates key-phrases into BERT embeddings to enhance relevance and diversity, achieving higher ROUGE scores. Abstractive models such as ATSumm [16] leverage auxiliary event information to produce fluent, human-like summaries even with sparse data. However, these approaches can be verbose when redundancy is not explicitly controlled and are computationally demanding, which constrains their use in real-time disaster response.

Another important line of work has focused on benchmark dataset construction, enabling the training and evaluation of supervised systems. ADSumm [17] introduced ground-truth summaries and key-phrases for eight disaster events, yielding 8-28% improvements in ROUGE scores for supervised models. ISSumSet [18], derived from TREC Incident Streams, added an evaluation benchmark but uses relatively coarse labels, limiting fine-grained analysis. Despite these contributions, there remains a scarcity of diverse, multilingual, and real-time datasets for testing scalable summarization systems.

Several studies have formulated summarization as a multi-objective optimization problem. Multi-Objective Ant Colony Optimization (MOACO)-based approaches [19][20] jointly optimize informativeness, diversity, and redundancy, producing balanced summaries. MOOTweetSumm+[21] combined graph-based LexRank features with differential evolution, improving ROUGE-2 by over 13% relative to baselines. These models are unsupervised and robust but typically treat tweets as independent units, overlooking the sequential flow of events that is crucial for situational awareness.

Hybrid classification–summarization pipelines have also been proposed to isolate actionable content before summarizing. Rudra et al. [22] used a two-stage approach that classifies tweets into situational and non-situational categories, followed by ILP-based summarization

Table 1. Comparative analysis of representative disaster tweet summarization approaches.

Approach	Technique	Strengths	Limitations
OntoDSumm [13]	Ontology-based tweet classification and summarization	Improves semantic coverage and relevance; filters noisy tweets effectively	Rely on predefined ontologies; struggles with novel terminology and informal language
OntoRealSumm [14]	Real-time ontology-driven summarization	Supports streaming updates; good for evolving events	Produces redundancy due to lack of explicit optimization; limited adaptability to unseen event types
IKDSumm [15]	BERT embeddings with key-phrase integration	Enhances semantic relevance and coverage; improves ROUGE scores	No explicit redundancy reduction; can generate verbose summaries
ATSumm [16]	Auxiliary-information-guided abstractive model	Produces fluent, human-like summaries; handles sparse data	Computationally heavy; less suitable for real-time scenarios
ADSumm [17]	Annotated dataset with ground-truth summaries, key-phrases, and relevance labels	Boosts supervised model performance; provides diverse event coverage	Limited number of events; not multilingual
ISSumSet [18]	Dataset from TREC Incident Streams	Enables benchmarking and model comparison	Coarse-grained annotations; limited for fine-grained evaluation
MOACO [19] [20]	Multi-objective Ant Colony Optimization	Balances coverage, diversity, redundancy	Treats tweets independently; ignores event timeline coherence
MOOTweetSumm+ [21]	Graph centrality + differential evolution	Improves diversity and informativeness; ROUGE-2 gains > 13 %	Still sensitive to noise and lacks temporal modeling
SEDOM-DD [24]	Spatial clustering and geotag-based sub-event detection	Improves granularity of situational updates	Relies on geotagged data, which is often missing
Deep Learning Models [25]	BLSTM + attention for situational classification	Outperforms traditional classifiers	Requires large, labeled datasets; less robust for low-resource settings

to maximize content-word coverage. Nguyen et al. [23] advanced this idea by adding interpretability, making summaries more transparent for decision-makers. While effective, these systems are computationally expensive, limiting their applicability to high-velocity data streams where rapid response is essential.

Finally, sub-event detection techniques have been developed to improve the granularity of summaries. SEDOM-DD [24] used spatial clustering and geotagging to detect fine-grained incidents, while deep learning classification models [25] employing Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BLSTM) and attention mechanisms outperformed traditional methods for situational tweet detection.

Despite notable progress, existing disaster tweet summarization approaches exhibit clear trade-offs. Ontology-based methods such as OntoDSumm and OntoRealSumm improve semantic relevance but rely on predefined concept hierarchies, limiting their adaptability to emerging terminology and informal language during evolving disasters. Embedding-based approaches like IKDSumm enhance semantic representation but do not explicitly address redundancy, often leading to verbose summaries. Abstractive models such as ATSumm produce fluent outputs but incur high computational costs and remain sensitive to noisy, sparse social media data.

In contrast, the proposed ACO-RNN framework explicitly combines redundancy-aware optimization and sequential modeling. Ant Colony Optimization

enables principled control of coverage, diversity, and redundancy, while the Recurrent Neural Network preserves temporal coherence across selected tweets. This hybrid design directly addresses the limitations observed in prior studies by jointly optimizing informativeness and coherence in a scalable, unsupervised setting.

A comparative overview of these representative approaches is presented in Table 1, summarizing their techniques, strengths, and limitations. Overall, these works reveal consistent progress yet leave key gaps: (i) the difficulty of handling noise and redundancy in large-scale streams, (ii) limited scalability and adaptability of ontology and neural systems in rapidly evolving crises, and (iii) the lack of explicit modeling of event progression and coherence. The proposed ACO-RNN framework directly addresses these challenges by using ACO to optimize for coverage, diversity, and minimal redundancy, and RNNs to preserve sequential flow, resulting in summaries that are both representative and coherent across disaster scenarios.

3. METHODOLOGY

The proposed framework (ACO-RNN) is designed to generate concise, informative, and coherent summaries of disaster-related tweets. It integrates four main components: (1) preprocessing to reduce noise, (2) Word2Vec embeddings to represent text semantically, (3) Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) to select representative and non-redundant sentences, and (4) a recurrent neural network (RNN) trained with gradient-based learning to ensure coherence in the final summaries. The overall process is illustrated in Figure 1 and discussed in detail in the following subsections.

Figure 1. Overall flow for Disaster tweet

3.1 Dataset

The study utilized four public datasets available: SandyHShoot, HydBlast, UFlood, and TyHagupit datasets collected by [22]. Data consistency is ensured through preprocessing, which eliminates noise and normalizes language for efficient model training. Source: http://cse.iitkgp.ac.in/~krudra/disaster_dataset.html

3.2 Data Preprocessing

Preprocessing plays a significant role in preparing unstructured disaster-related tweets for summarization. This step tackles issues such as missing values and duplicate content through key sub-processes, including tokenization, stemming, stop word removal, and keyword recognition.

3.2.1 Tokenization

Tokenization involves breaking down raw text into smaller units, such as words, phrases, or subwords, serving as the foundation for various NLP tasks [26]. Tokenization is represented in Equation (1).

$$T(x) = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n\} \tag{1}$$

Where x is the tweet, and t_i are tokens.

3.2.2 Stemming

Stemming transforms words into their root form by removing prefixes and suffixes. For instance, "walking" is reduced to "walk," consolidating different word forms with similar meanings. Additionally, verbs are converted to their base form; for example, "was" and "being" become "be" [27]. The stemming process is defined in Equation (2).

$$S(t) = \text{root}(t), \forall t \in T^M(x) \tag{2}$$

3.2.3 Stop word removal

Common words such as "the," "is," and "at" are frequently used but often add unnecessary noise to the data, contributing little to the main message of a tweet. Removing these stop words enhances the model's ability to focus on essential information by filtering out less meaningful terms. While these words have semantic significance, they can interfere with similarity calculations if retained. Typically, stop words include pronouns, conjunctions, and prepositions. Therefore, a predefined list of stop words is applied to the text, and any word that matches the list is discarded. The specific words on the list depend on the type of data being processed [27].

$$T'(x) = T(x) \setminus \{t_i | t_i \in \text{StopWords}\} \tag{3}$$

3.2.4. Keyword recognition

This step involves identifying key terms associated with disasters, such as "earthquake," "evacuation," and "flood," which are prioritized in the model to highlight important disaster-related information. Equation (4) illustrates the keyword recognition process. The pre-processed output is displayed in Figure 2.

$$K(x) = \{t_i | t_i \in DisasterKeywords\} \quad (4)$$

Combine with tokens in Equation (5),

$$PreprocessedData(x) = T'(x) \cup K(w) \quad (5)$$

Figure 2. Preprocessed output

3.3 Feature extraction using Word2Vec

Word2Vec [28] is used for feature extraction to enrich the summarization of disaster-related tweets by capturing the semantic relationships between words. It represents each word as a dense vector in a high-dimensional space, which helps create a context model crucial for unstructured, context-sensitive data like disaster tweets.

Word2Vec, an open-source toolkit for generating word vectors, quantifies word correlations based on the distance between word vectors. The closer two vectors are, the more semantically related the words are. It is widely used in NLP tasks such as text categorization, sentiment analysis, and clustering.

$$P(w_c | w_t) = \frac{\exp(u_{w_c} \cdot u_{w_t})}{\sum_{w' \in V} \exp(u_{w'} \cdot u_{w_t})} \quad (6)$$

Where w_t is the target word, w_c are context words, v are embeddings, and V is the vocabulary. Word2vec can generate

word vectors using two models: the Continuous Bag-of-Words (CBOW) and the Skip-gram Model [29]. The primary goal of CBOW is to forecast the likelihood of the centre word based on the surrounding context, whereas the Skip-gram Model predicts the context by "skipping some symbols" surrounding the centre word. The CBOW Model requires a lot of time, and the dimension of the sliding window limits the impact of training.

However, the Skip-gram Model has greater semantics reliability, but it also requires a lot of computation and requires an extended period to train. The CBOW model's goal is to forecast the centre word w_t by using the context words that surround it. In the framework of the model, the centre word's probability is maximized.

Figure 3. Structure of CBOW and Skip-gram

This is the objective function in Equation (7):

$$J_{CBOW} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \log P(w_t | w_{t-m}, \dots, w_{t-1}, w_{t+1}, \dots, w_{t+m}) \quad (7)$$

The corpus's total word count is denoted by T. The central word is w_t . The context words inside a window size m are $w_{(t-m)} \dots w_{(t+m)}$. The probability P (w_t | context) is calculated using softmax as follows in Equation (8):

$$P(w_t | context) = \frac{\exp(V_{w_t} \cdot V_{context})}{\sum_{w' \in V} \exp(V_{w'} \cdot V_{context})} \quad (8)$$

Where the vector for the central word, w_t is denoted by V_{w_t} . The aggregating vectors of the context words is called $V_{context}$. The vocabulary size is denoted by V . The process the Skip-gram model operates is by using the centre word w_t to predict the context words w_{t+j} (for $j = -m, \dots, m, j \neq 0$). Its objective is shown in Equation (9):

$$J_{Skip-gram} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{-m \leq j \leq m, j \neq 0} \log P(w_{t+j} | w_t) \quad (9)$$

There, softmax is used to calculate $P(w_{t+j} | w_t)$ as follows in Equation (10):

$$P(w_{t+j} | w_t) = \frac{\exp(V_{w_{t+j}} \cdot V_{w_t})}{\sum_{w' \in V} \exp(V_{w'} \cdot V_{w_t})} \quad (10)$$

Figure 4. Architectures of Word2Vec Models: Skip-gram and CBOW

AS shown in **Figure 4** illustrates the two main architectures of Word2Vec. The Skip-gram model predicts surrounding context words from a given target word, while the CBOW (Continuous Bag of Words) model predicts the target word from surrounding context words. Both approaches are applied to represent tweets as dense semantic vectors for disaster summarization.

3.4 Summarization using ACO and RNN

The ACO-RNN is a hybrid model tailored for disaster tweet summarization, integrating ACO [30], gradient-based learning [31], and Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) techniques. ACO, inspired by ant foraging behavior, is used to identify optimal sequences in text, reducing redundancy by selecting non-overlapping, representative sentences. Gradient-based learning then fine-tunes the model by minimizing errors through iterative weight adjustments, improving the summary's accuracy over time. Meanwhile, RNN-based spatial recurrence allows the model to capture temporal and positional dependencies within tweets, ensuring coherence and contextual understanding even with fragmented text. This integrated approach enhances summarization by making the model capable of handling large noisy datasets, and delivering accurate, concise, and non-redundant summaries for disaster-related tweets.

3.4.1 Ant colony optimization (ACO) for sentence selection

Ants' natural foraging activity serves as the model for the bio-inspired algorithm known as ACO. In the context of text summarization, ACO assists in identifying optimal sequences of text

features and sentences by simulating ant pathfinding, where ants discover paths with the least redundancy. This process helps reduce overlapping content by selecting sentences that best represent the tweet data. Optimization of ACO parameters such as pheromone evaporation rate and heuristic factors enhances its efficiency, making it particularly effective for large, noisy datasets.

Ant colonies' ability to locate the fastest path from a food source to their nests requiring the use of visual aids served as the inspiration for a computerized method known as ACO. Ants use a specific quantity of pheromones to form a line and exchange messages with one another while they are hunting. People that are unable to detect the scent continue to travel erratically. When more ants are drawn to a certain path to find the shortest one, the pheromones of that trail increase. Figure 4 shows how the ACO flows. Probability of choosing the next node and ant uses a probabilistic rule to select the subsequent node j at each step in Equation (11):

$$P_{ij}(s) = \begin{cases} \frac{[\tau_{ij}(t)]^\alpha \cdot [\eta_{ij}]^\beta}{\sum_{k \in allowed} [\tau_{ik}(t)]^\alpha \cdot [\eta_{ik}]^\beta} & \text{if } j \in allowed \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

The probability of traveling from node i to node j at time t is represented by $P_{ij}(s)$. $\tau_{ij}(t)$ are the pheromone levels at time t on the path connecting i and j . Heuristic information, such as the inverse of the difference among i and j , is represented by η_{ij} . α : Pheromone effect weight. β : Heuristic influence weight. A group of nodes that the ant continues to avoid is known as "allowed." The following rule is used to update the pheromone levels on each path following Equation (12) is the completion of a cycle:

$$\tau_{ij}(t+1) = (1 - \rho) \cdot \tau_{ij}(t) + \Delta\tau_{ij} \quad (12)$$

Where ρ , a constant among 0 and 1, is the pheromone evaporation rate. $\Delta\tau_{ij}$ Ants left a pheromone on the path (i,j) :

$$\Delta\tau_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^m \begin{cases} \frac{Q}{L_k} & \text{if ant } k \text{ use path } (i,j) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Where m represents the ant population. The quantity of pheromone deposited is represented by the constant Q . The length of ant K 's travel is denoted by L_k .

To begin the ant algorithm, the ants are dispersed at random to each city, which serves as the starting point for each ant [32]. Based on specific probability, such an ant will choose the next city. The pheromone matrix, distance matrix, and parameters all affect this probability. The selection is made repeatedly until each ant has

made one trip to each city. That is the algorithm's initial cycle, which continues until the stopping criteria are met. Every cycle, the total of the pheromone matrix is refreshed, and the path is systematically altered.

3.4.2 Gradient-based learning

The proposed hybrid approach also incorporates Gradient-Based Learning, a technique crucial to neural network training. Through gradient descent, it adjusts weights to minimize the error between the generated summary and an ideal summary. By iteratively refining weights to reduce loss, the model increases its accuracy, ultimately learning to produce concise, high-relevance summaries over time. Gradient learning fine-tunes the neural network, improving its understanding of disaster-related language and optimizing summarization outputs.

The foundation of gradient-based learning is the observation that minimizing a suitably seamless, continuous function is typically far simpler than minimizing a discrete function. By calculating the effect of slight changes in the parameter values on the loss function, the loss function can be reduced. The gradient of the loss function about the parameters serves as a measurement of performance. When the gradient vector can be calculated analytically, effective learning algorithms can be developed. Many gradient-based learning methods with continuously valued parameters are based on technique [33].

The set of variables in the processes outlined is a X real-valued vector, about which $F(X)$ is continuous and nearly always differentiable. The gradient descent process is the most straightforward minimization technique in this situation, where X is iteratively changed as following Equation (14):

$$X_i = X_{i-1} - \epsilon \frac{\partial F(X)}{\partial X} \quad (14)$$

ϵ is a scalar constant in the most basic scenario. Variable ϵ is employed in more intricate procedures, or it could be utilized in Newton or quasi-Newton techniques to establish a matrix with diagonal elements or an estimation of the inverted Hessian matrix. In gradient descent, X_i represents the updated parameter values after the i -th iteration, while X_{i-1} is the previous parameter set. The learning rate ϵ controls how much the parameters change, and the gradient $\frac{\partial F(X)}{\partial X}$ indicates the direction in which the function $F(X)$ increases the most. By moving in the opposite direction of the gradient, the algorithm minimizes the function to find the optimal parameters. Another possibility is to employ the conjugated gradient approach.

The stochastic gradient algorithm, often known as the web-based update, is a widely used minimization technique. It involves employing a noisy, or estimated, variant of the parameters vector updated using the median gradients. X is updated based on a single sample in the most prevalent case.

$$X_i = X_{i-1} - \epsilon \frac{\partial F^{(i)}(X)}{\partial X} \quad (15)$$

Figure 5. Flowchart of the Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) process.

As shown in Figure 5 illustrates the main steps of the ACO algorithm, starting from initialization, assigning ants to cities, constructing routes, updating pheromone information, and checking the stopping condition until the final optimal solution is reached.

This procedure usually connects faster than second-order algorithms and traditional gradient descent techniques on large training sets with overlapping tests; however, the coefficient vectors fluctuate in typical directions.

Momentum-Based Gradient Descent Momentum can be added to gradient descent to decrease oscillations and speed convergence in Equations (16) and (17):

$$v^{(l)} = \gamma \cdot v^{(l-1)} + \eta \cdot \nabla F(X) \quad (16)$$

$$X^{(l)} = X^{(l-1)} - v^{(l)} \quad (17)$$

The velocity vector that generates gradients in this case is denoted by $v^{(l)}$. γ Momentum coefficient, which ranges from 0 to 1. Momentum speeds up convergence and aids the model in overcoming tiny local minima.

3.4.3 Recurrent neural network (RNN)

RNN structures, particularly spatial recurrence, enable the model to handle the temporal and sequential nature of tweets. The RNN captures dependencies between words and sentences, allowing the model to maintain coherence across tweets, even with fragmented or irregular language. Spatial awareness allows it to consider the position and context of terms, enhancing its grasp of critical disaster-related concepts and events.

The initial level neural unit, final layer neural unit, and concealed layer neural unit comprise the RNN model. Similar to the conventional neural network model, it maintains the same structure. Nonetheless, the unique characteristic of the RNN model is the interconnectedness of the neuron nodes between the concealed layers. The input of the concealing layer consists of the output of the concealing layer at the previous instant and the input value w of the inputs layered [34]. The link is explained by equation (18), it shows g represents the output of the concealed layer, w is the weight input to the layer, and $g_{(s-1)}$ is the output from the previous time step.

$$g = e(w + g_{s-1}) \quad (18)$$

The neurons in the RNN neural network's concealed component feature a feedback process that may transmit contextual information and anticipate sequenced samples, ensuring that the RNN model has efficient handling. It is widely used in the creation of visual information, automatic transformation, harmony synthesis, and text classification. Every system neuron node in Equation (19)'s sub-development of signals forward propagation features a non-linear s-type activated process:

$$\text{sigm}(w) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-w}} \quad (19)$$

Each network neuron's weight and threshold are repeatedly adjusted using the gradient descent technique in the error back propagation sub process to reach the target of the least error function value. The cost function can be defined as following Equation (20), it shows where $g_{x,a}(w)$ is the predicted output, ε is the target, and the function measures the error between predicted and actual outputs.

$$I(x, a; w, \varepsilon) = \frac{1}{2} \|g_{x,a}(w) - \varepsilon\|^2 \quad (20)$$

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the evaluation of the proposed ACO-RNN framework for disaster tweet summarization. Experiments were conducted on four disaster-related datasets: TyHagupit, SandyHShoot, HydBlast, and UFlood. The implementation was carried out in Python 3.10.1 using TensorFlow, and evaluation relied on ROUGE-1, ROUGE-2, and ROUGE-L metrics, reported in terms of precision, recall, and F1-score. These measures collectively provide a balanced assessment of lexical coverage, phrase-level informativeness, and sentence-level fluency.

4.1 Impact of Pre-processing on the Proposed Approach

Pre-processing plays a crucial role in enhancing summarization quality for disaster-related tweets, which are short, noisy, and often contain redundant content. In this work, the Raw (Baseline) setting refers to lightly cleaned tweets (basic tokenization and removal of unusable symbols) but without stopword removal, normalization, or stemming. As shown in Table 2, this baseline yields the lowest ROUGE scores across all datasets, confirming that noise and lexical variability negatively affect summarization performance.

Applying stopword removal results in a small but consistent improvement suggesting that eliminating high-frequency function words helps the model focus more on informative tokens. Normalization further boosts performance by reducing spelling and capitalization irregularities, which strengthens word embeddings and improves semantic matching. The largest single-step gain is observed with stemming, which consolidates word variants (e.g., “evacuate,” “evacuated”) into a

Table 2. Impact of Pre-Processing on The Proposed Approach Performance.

Dataset	Preprocessing Pipeline	ROUGE-1			ROUGE-2			ROUGE-L		
		P	R	F1	P	R	F1	P	R	F1
TyHagupit	Raw (Baseline)	0.516	0.49	0.503	0.21	0.205	0.207	0.388	0.370	0.379
	Stopword Removal	0.538	0.523	0.529	0.232	0.229	0.230	0.410	0.402	0.406
	Normalization	0.554	0.538	0.546	0.246	0.251	0.248	0.426	0.418	0.422
	Stemming	0.572	0.563	0.567	0.262	0.267	0.264	0.446	0.430	0.438
	Full	0.603	0.625	0.614	0.289	0.295	0.292	0.458	0.470	0.464
SandyHShoot	Raw (Baseline)	0.540	0.516	0.528	0.146	0.149	0.148	0.398	0.379	0.388
	Stopword Removal	0.561	0.528	0.544	0.169	0.167	0.168	0.418	0.406	0.412
	Normalization	0.575	0.556	0.565	0.189	0.187	0.188	0.434	0.427	0.43
	Stemming	0.594	0.568	0.581	0.216	0.208	0.212	0.456	0.438	0.447
	Full	0.62	0.603	0.611	0.243	0.247	0.245	0.476	0.482	0.479
HyBlast	Raw (Baseline)	0.504	0.476	0.49	0.182	0.188	0.185	0.356	0.362	0.359
	Stopword Removal	0.526	0.51	0.518	0.205	0.202	0.204	0.38	0.376	0.378
	Normalization	0.543	0.526	0.534	0.221	0.216	0.219	0.402	0.395	0.398
	Stemming	0.562	0.545	0.553	0.237	0.242	0.24	0.428	0.423	0.425
	Full	0.587	0.587	0.587	0.268	0.274	0.271	0.47	0.454	0.462
UFlood	Raw (Baseline)	0.514	0.494	0.504	0.181	0.172	0.176	0.378	0.376	0.377
	Stopword Removal	0.536	0.532	0.534	0.203	0.196	0.201	0.401	0.396	0.398
	Normalization	0.556	0.522	0.539	0.219	0.217	0.218	0.415	0.415	0.415
	Stemming	0.574	0.562	0.568	0.235	0.227	0.231	0.436	0.430	0.433
	Full	0.601	0.603	0.602	0.270	0.264	0.267	0.481	0.463	0.472

single representation and thus enhances the quality of selected sentences.

The combined pipeline (stopword removal + normalization + stemming) consistently delivers the highest ROUGE-1, ROUGE-2, and ROUGE-L scores across all four datasets. For instance, on the TyHagupit dataset, ROUGE-1 F1 improves from 0.503 with the raw baseline to 0.614 with the full pipeline. Similar trends are observed for SandyHShoot, HydBlast, and UFlood, confirming that the preprocessing steps are complementary and most effective when applied together. These results highlight that preprocessing is not a trivial step but a key contributor to improving the coverage, coherence, and informativeness of disaster tweet summaries.

As shown in Table 2 the proposed ACO–RNN framework demonstrates strong and consistent performance across all four disaster tweet datasets, namely TyHagupit, SandyHShoot, HydBlast, and UFlood. The ROUGE F1-scores indicate that the model not only captures the essential content (ROUGE-1) but also preserves semantic relations between phrases (ROUGE-2) and maintains structural coherence (ROUGE-L). These results

confirm the robustness of the hybrid design, showing that the combination of ACO for redundancy reduction and RNN for sequence modeling generalizes effectively across diverse disaster scenarios.

Fig 6. Impact of Preprocessing on TyHagupit Dataset (ROUGE-1 F1)

Figure 6 illustrates the effect of different preprocessing steps (stopword removal, normalization, stemming) on the TyHagupit dataset. The results demonstrate that the complete preprocessing pipeline yields the highest ROUGE-1 F1 score, confirming the importance of

comprehensive text cleaning for disaster tweet summarization.

Table 3 presents the ROUGE F1-scores achieved by the proposed ACO-RNN framework across the four disaster tweet datasets. The results show that the model demonstrates strong and consistent performance across all datasets. The ROUGE F1-scores indicate that the framework not only captures essential content (ROUGE-1) but also preserves semantic relationships between phrases (ROUGE-2) and maintains structural coherence (ROUGE-L).

Table 3. Rouge F1-Scores of the Proposed Aco-RNN Framework Across Four Disaster Tweet Datasets (Tyhagupit, Sandyhshoot, Hydblast, And Uflood).

Dataset	ROUGE-1 (F1)	ROUGE-2 (F1)	ROUGE-L (F1)
Tyhagupit	0.614	0.292	0.464
SandyHShoot	0.611	0.245	0.479
HydBlast	0.587	0.271	0.462
UFlood	0.602	0.267	0.472

4.2 Performance Comparison with Baselines

The proposed ACO-RNN framework was compared against four established baselines: IKDSumm [15], OntoDSumm [13], ATSumm [16] and OntoRealSumm [14]. These methods were chosen as they represent commonly used approaches for disaster tweet summarization and provide a meaningful benchmark for evaluating the robustness of our method. Results in **Table 4** and **Figure 7** demonstrate that ACO-RNN consistently outperforms all baselines across datasets, with clear gains in precision, recall, and F1-scores for ROUGE-1, ROUGE-2, and ROUGE-L.

On TyHagupit, ACO-RNN achieved a ROUGE-1 F1 of **0.614**, outperforming OntoDSumm (**0.47**) and OntoRealSumm (**0.49**). Importantly, the gain in ROUGE-2 F1 (**0.292** vs. **0.19** for OntoRealSumm) reflects the ability of ACO-RNN to capture phrase-level dependencies, which are critical when tweets contain fragmented but semantically linked expressions. For ROUGE-L, ACO-RNN attained **0.464**, again surpassing all baselines.

On SandyHShoot, the framework delivered a ROUGE-1 F1 of **0.611**, ROUGE-2 of **0.245** and ROUGE-L F1 of **0.479**. In contrast, OntoRealSumm achieved 0.51, 0.20, and 0.29, respectively. These results underline the framework's ability to handle noisy and fragmented text while maintaining sentence-level fluency.

For HydBlast, which is particularly challenging due to high redundancy in user reports, ACO-RNN

achieved a ROUGE-1 F1 of **0.587**, ROUGE-2 F1 of **0.271** and ROUGE-L of **0.462**. In comparison, ATSumm, the strongest baseline on this dataset, attained only **0.52**, **0.28**, and **0.34**. These results show that the ant colony optimization component effectively discourages redundant sentence inclusion, while the neural layer retains key informative content.

Finally, on UFlood, the model produced ROUGE-1, ROUGE-2, and ROUGE-L F1 scores of **0.602**, **0.267**, and **0.472**, again surpassing all baseline systems by a comfortable margin. The gains are particularly striking when compared to OntoDSumm (**0.46**, **0.18**, **0.27**), highlighting the substantial margin of improvement offered by ACO-RNN.

Compared to previous studies, the proposed ACO-RNN framework demonstrates consistent and measurable improvements across all datasets and ROUGE metrics. Ontology-based approaches typically achieve ROUGE-1 F1-scores in the range of 0.46 to 0.51, while embedding-based and abstractive methods report scores between 0.48 and 0.58 depending on the dataset. In contrast, ACO-RNN achieves ROUGE-1 F1-scores ranging from 0.587 to 0.614, representing relative improvements of 8 to 13 percent over the strongest baselines.

The improvements are particularly evident in ROUGE-2 and ROUGE-L scores, indicating that ACO-RNN captures both phrase-level semantic relations and sentence-level coherence more effectively than previous methods. These results confirm that integrating optimization-based redundancy control with recurrent sequence modeling yields summaries that are not only more informative but also more coherent than those produced by existing approaches.

4.3 Discussion

Preprocessing proved to be a decisive factor in the quality of summaries produced by the framework. The lightly cleaned raw baseline yielded the lowest ROUGE scores, particularly for noisier datasets such as HydBlast, where irregular spelling and redundancy are common. Stopword removal offered small but consistent gains, while normalization and stemming contributed the largest improvements by consolidating word forms and reducing vocabulary fragmentation. The combined pipeline consistently delivered the highest ROUGE-1, ROUGE-2, and ROUGE-L scores, confirming that these steps are complementary and critical for maximizing the effectiveness of the downstream ACO-RNN model.

Table 4: Performance Comparison of the Proposed Approach Against Baseline Methods.

Datasets	Approach	Rouge 1			Rouge 2			Rouge L		
		Precision	Recall	F1 score	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Precision	Recall	F1 score
TyHagupit	IKDSumm	-	-	0.48	-	-	0.22	-	-	0.32
	OntoDSumm	0.48	0.45	0.47	0.20	0.19	0.20	0.32	0.29	0.30
	ATSumm	-	-	0.48	-	-	0.24	-	-	0.30
	OntoRealSumm	0.50	0.48	0.49	0.19	0.18	0.19	0.28	0.27	0.28
	ACO-RNN	0.603	0.625	0.614	0.289	0.295	0.292	0.458	0.47	0.464
SandyHShoot	IKDSumm	-	-	0.57	-	-	0.29	-	-	0.42
	OntoDSumm	0.55	0.53	0.54	0.24	0.21	0.23	0.30	0.28	0.29
	ATSumm	-	-	0.58	-	-	0.30	-	-	0.41
	OntoRealSumm	0.56	0.48	0.51	0.21	0.18	0.20	0.31	0.27	0.29
	ACO-RNN	0.619	0.603	0.611	0.243	0.247	0.245	0.476	0.482	0.479
HydBlast	IKDSumm	-	-	0.47	-	-	0.20	-	-	0.29
	OntoDSumm	0.48	0.48	0.47	0.20	0.19	0.19	0.29	0.28	0.28
	ATSumm	-	-	0.52	-	-	0.28	-	-	0.34
	OntoRealSumm	0.49	0.44	0.47	0.19	0.17	0.18	0.29	0.27	0.28
	ACO-RNN	0.574	0.6	0.587	0.268	0.274	0.271	0.47	0.454	0.462
UFlood	IKDSumm	-	-	0.48	-	-	0.19	-	-	0.29
	OntoDSumm	0.47	0.45	0.46	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.27	0.27	0.27
	ATSumm	-	-	0.44	-	-	0.20	-	-	0.32
	OntoRealSumm	0.46	0.45	0.46	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.27	0.26	0.27
	ACO-RNN	0.601	0.603	0.602	0.27	0.264	0.267	0.481	0.463	0.472

Figure 7. Performance Comparison of the Proposed Approach Against Baseline Methods

The improvements offered by ACO-RNN are consistent across datasets and evaluation metrics. Ontology-based models (OntoDSumm, OntoRealSumm) provide domain relevance but lack flexibility when faced with evolving and informal Twitter language. ATSumm performs relatively well in certain cases but struggles with redundancy and coherence. ACO-RNN's integration of optimization and recurrent modeling addresses these limitations by ensuring both content selection (via ACO) and sequential fluency (via RNN). From a practical perspective, ACO-RNN provides disaster managers and humanitarian organizations with summaries that are factually rich, coherent, and easy to interpret under time pressure. Its ability to filter repetitive, low-value tweets while maintaining narrative coherence ensures the production of reliable situational reports. Across all datasets, the model improves ROUGE-1 F1-scores by margins of 0.10–0.13 over the strongest baselines, demonstrating scalability and robustness. These improvements highlight the framework's potential for real-time crisis informatics applications, where rapid and accurate information extraction is essential.

The observed performance trends of the proposed ACO-RNN framework are consistent with findings reported in prior disaster tweet summarization studies. Like ontology-based and embedding-driven approaches, the proposed method demonstrates strong gains in ROUGE-1, confirming its ability to capture salient content. At the same time, the improvements in ROUGE-2 and ROUGE-L align with observations from neural and optimization-based techniques, which emphasize phrase-level informativeness and coherence. Across all datasets, the relative performance ordering between baseline methods remains stable, indicating that ACO-RNN enhances summary quality without contradicting established empirical patterns. This consistency suggests that the proposed framework builds upon, rather than diverges from, existing techniques while offering systematic improvements through integrated redundancy control and sequential modelling.

4.4 Limitations

While the proposed ACO-RNN framework demonstrates consistent improvements over existing approaches, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the use of Ant Colony Optimization introduces additional computational overhead, which may affect scalability in strict real-time scenarios with extremely high tweet volumes. Although the framework remains suitable for near

real-time analysis, further optimization would be required for large-scale streaming deployments.

Second, the framework relies on Word2Vec embeddings, which provide static word representations and may not fully capture evolving contextual meanings or sarcasm commonly present in social media text. More advanced contextual embeddings could further enhance semantic representation.

Third, the evaluation is limited to four English-language disaster tweet datasets. While these datasets are widely used benchmarks, the generalization of the proposed approach to multilingual or cross-lingual disaster data has not been explored in this study.

Finally, the evaluation relies on ROUGE metrics, which primarily measure lexical overlap and may not fully reflect factual correctness or human judgment of summary usefulness. Incorporating human evaluation could provide deeper insights into summary quality.

5. CONCLUSION

Disaster tweet summarization remains a challenging task due to the noisy, unstructured, and rapidly evolving nature of social media content. In this study, we proposed ACO-RNN, a hybrid summarization framework that integrates Word2Vec-based semantic representations with Ant Colony Optimization for redundancy-aware content selection and recurrent neural modeling for preserving temporal coherence. Supported by an effective preprocessing pipeline, the proposed framework addresses key limitations of existing methods related to redundancy control, coherence preservation, and scalability.

Extensive experiments conducted on four benchmark disaster tweet datasets demonstrate that ACO-RNN consistently outperforms well-established baseline approaches. The observed improvements in ROUGE-1, ROUGE-2, and ROUGE-L precision, recall, and F1-scores confirm the effectiveness of combining multi-objective optimization with sequential modeling. The generated summaries are concise, coherent, and semantically informative, making them suitable for supporting situational awareness and decision-making during disaster response.

Despite these strengths, the framework has certain limitations. The use of optimization-based selection introduces additional computational overhead, which may affect strict real-time deployment under

very high data volumes. In addition, reliance on static word embeddings limits the ability to fully capture evolving contextual meanings and informal language patterns common in social media. The evaluation is also restricted to English-language datasets and automated metrics.

Future research will focus on improving computational efficiency through lightweight optimization strategies and parallel or hardware-accelerated implementations. Incorporating contextual embedding models may further enhance semantic representation and adaptability to evolving language. Extending the framework to multilingual and cross-lingual disaster data, as well as integrating human-centered evaluation and adaptive learning mechanisms, represents promising directions for improving robustness and practical applicability in real-world disaster management scenarios.

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